

Gas chromatograms of molecular extracts from WBPH-resistant Rathu Heenati and susceptible TN1 rice plants. IRRRI, 1988.

250 °C, at 5 °C per min. One μ l of the extracts was used for analysis on the splitless mode.

The figure shows qualitative and quantitative differences between molecular distillate extracts of resistant Rathu Heenati and susceptible TN1. This may reflect different volatile composition of the odors produced by rice plants that influence the insect locating its host plant. □

Ptb 10 — a promising donor of gall midge (GM) resistance

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During the 1986 rainy season a severe epidemic of GM in Srikakulam District destroyed resistant varieties Phalguna and Surekha (derivatives of Siam 29). Grain yield losses were estimated at 50-

Reaction of donors and derivatives to GM. A.P., India, 1988.

Designation	Parentage	GM incidence ^a (% SS)			
		30 DT		50 DT	
		HB	TB	HB	TB
Ptb 10	Donor	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Ptb 18	Donor	20	1.45	20	2.07
Ptb 21	Donor	40	4.26	40	4.36
Ptb 33	Donor	20	2.18	20	3.67
Siam 29	Donor	45	4.93	100	24.52
Leuang 152	Donor	45	6.51	100	29.56
OB677	Donor	30	2.97	30	3.20
Phalguna	IR8/Siam 29	90	22.25	95	40.99
Surekha	IR8/Siam 29	65	7.31	100	49.07
Jaya (susceptible check)	TN1/IR8	70	9.16	90	32.69

^aHB = hill basis, TB = tiller basis.

90%. We evaluated certain potential new donors of resistance to the GM population of the district during 1988 rainy season at Panukuvalasa, a hot spot location.

Seven proven donors and two derivatives of Siam 29 were planted in six rows of 16 hills each at 15- × 15-cm spacing. GM incidence was recorded at 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT) on hills and tillers from 20 preselected hills/entry.

Among the Ptb series, only Ptb 10 had no silvershoots (SS) (see table). The

three other donors had 20-40% SS/hill at 50 DT.

Phalguna and Surekha, the predominant varieties of the north coastal district of A.P., had 95-100% SS/hill and 41-49%/tiller at 50 DT. Susceptible check Jaya had 90 and 33%, respectively. Proven donors Siam 29 and Leuang 152 had 100% GM/hill and 24-30%/tiller.

These results show the need to reorient the breeding programs for GM resistance, using Ptb 10 as one of the donors. □

Excess water tolerance

Changes in shoot growth in response to partial submergence

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We tested tall and semitall rice varieties for growth and yield under normal and semideep water (55-60 cm) in a tank experiment during 1980 wet season (kharif). Seedlings (30-d-old) were transplanted in two tanks, with three replications. At 25 d after transplanting, one tank was flooded to 55-60 cm water depth, the other was kept at 5-10 cm. Plants were sampled at 20 and 45 d after submergence, flowering, and maturity.

At 20 d after submergence, 55-60 cm water reduced dry weight 23% and leaf area per tiller 58%. At flowering, they increased 41 and 26%, respectively (see table). Excess water significantly increased dry weight/ tiller at maturity. In almost all varieties, specific leaf weight (SLW) increased significantly at 20 d after submergence. Crop growth rate under 55-60 cm water was reduced by 50% 20-45 d after submergence, but increased during pre-anthesis (45 d after submergence to flowering) and post-anthesis (flowering to maturity).

Semitall Jagannath showed drastic reduction in shoot growth under 55-60 cm water, Janaki and CR1030 (tall) had maximum stability. □